

Empowering education: the transformative impact of information communication technologies on teaching and learning

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ABSTRACT: The widespread adoption of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has significantly impact the global education system. Developing countries have also experienced an increasing trend in ICT and e-learning usage over the past decade including Pakistan. Implementation of ICT in the process of learning is considered to be the wide range reform in the education sector. Educational policy of Pakistan has specifically emphasized the integration of ICTs and technology-based teaching in schools and universities. Moreover, the national professional standards for teachers encourage the use of ICTs in classrooms and the development of e-learning platforms for teaching and learning. Therefore, this study aims to measure the influence of ICT determinants on teaching & learning in higher education institutions (HEIs) in the Hazara region, Pakistan. This region is characterized as an underdeveloped and marginalized. Data was collected through questionnaire from a sample size of 323 including both faculty and students. Mix method approach, Relative Importance Index (RII), thematic analysis and Binary logistic regression have been used in this study, using SPSS (version-27) to analyze the data. It was found that ICT determinants like availability and usability have positive influence ($P < .05$) on teaching whereas accessibility, usability and usefulness have positive influence on learning respectively. RII findings also highlights that the use of internet and computer improve students learning and help teachers in getting supportive materials for teaching. Therefore, policy recommendations will help decision makers to create favorable framework as well as future course of action for effective ICT integration at underdeveloped and marginalized regions.

Keywords: Higher education in 21st century, Teaching and learning, Educational technologies, ICT integration

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1. Introduction

Education is the best mean that provides unity between students and educators, as well as develops confidence and independence within the students (Kirmani et al. 2021). Information Communication and Technology (ICT) plays a significant role in achieving these traits and has become the major source for fundamental change in the classroom. ICT implementation in universities has recently gained momentum due to the technological revolution and advance implementation of the internet as the medium of communication (Memarian 2020). The term ICT is defined, as a “set of diverse technological resources and tools used for the purpose to; communicate, create, find, store and retrieve information”. These technologies include internet, computers, telephony and broadcasting technologies like radio and television (Zuhir et al. 2021).

Currently, ICT integration has undergone significant innovations, resulting in transformative effects on human life and profound impacts on societies that have completely reshaped people's working patterns, thinking and way of life (Ghavifekr et al. 2012). ICT has been significantly rising in education sector over the recent past, and now the future learning environment is difficult and even impossible without ICT (Tsegay et al. 2022). The significant impact and its crucial role in the processes of digitalization, globalization and information dissemination cannot be ignored (Habib et al. 2021). This revolution has transformed the way information is accessed, preserved and retrieved across the globe by transitioning to a digital system (Zuhir et al. 2021). Moreover, learning and knowledge sharing approaches have become increasingly dependent on the utilization of digital devices and internet.

ICT has employed its influence in all fields of life including education. A greater change in education (teaching, learning, and research) has been observed in the last three decades (Chandio 2021). ICT usage can develop students' learning attitude, motivation and interaction by enhancing their flexibility and independence of learning new things (Ghavifekr and Rosdy 2015). It gathers, organizes and uses information in various forms such as, images, sound, text and videos etc. through computers (Hamidi et al. 2011). Such educational technologies provides open education practice environment and make the information content easier to find, access and retrieve. These steps are central to teaching and learning and together they constitute a dynamic digital learning process (Asad et al. 2020).

ICT application creates competitive environment, increases efficiency, enhances services to faculty and students and generates enrich learning experiences (Termit and Samli 2014). The study of Browne et al. (2006) exhibits that in United Kingdom 95% of HEIs are utilizing ICT indicating the growing trust in ICT focus academic activities. Coleman et al. (2016) highlighted the process of transformation from teacher-centered to students-centered in the learning environment. According to Ndibalema (2021), the application of multi-media technologies (audio, video, graphics and animations) create productive environment, interest, and motivation and quality delivery of lecture in classroom activity. The utilization of internet in education has progress significantly due to the rise of online classes and the availability of study materials and e-books. The invention and availability of the dynamic, portable mobile devices like smart phones, laptops and tablets have greatly expanded their usage. This has empowered both the educator and students to access academic resources over the internet from any location (Kunwar et al. 2022).

Pakistan has been striving to bring reforms to the educational sector. Millions of dollars have been invested to introduce IT in the field of education, and majority are spent on development of human resource and provision of infrastructure (Hira 2021). Qamar (2004), found that Pakistan considered ICT as its lifeline for development in the 21st century. Consequently, cautious ICT policies have been designed for utilization of ICT particularly in the field of education, but lack of resources, budget, faculty motivation,

political pressure and power supply are some constraints in the way of its implementation (Sohail and Ahmad 2017).

Several studies highlights the adoption and usage of ICT in HEIs of Pakistan (Khan et al. 2018; Ali et al. 2015; Shaikh & Khoja 2011 and Nisar et al. 2011). However, all these studies lack focus on rural, underdeveloped and marginalized regions, where HEIs lack basic ICTs infrastructure. In the process of globalization the role of ICT cannot be denied; however, HEIs in Pakistan, particularly in the underdeveloped Hazara region, are deficient in ICT infrastructure and ICT tools availability. The availability of Internet, its connectivity, speed and power supply and the active use of ICT for teaching and learning are serious issues in the region that have lagged behind the region from development (Humbhi & Tareen, 2021). This situation creates a compelling need to investigate the impact of ICT integration on teaching and learning in HEIs of Hazara region, Pakistan.

ICT in Pakistan's Perspective

Pakistan exhibits comparatively a low literacy rate even in comparison with the other third world countries like Sri Lanka, Nepal and Ukraine etc (UNDP 2021). Majority of its population reside in rural areas, facing constraints in terms of resources and essential necessities. Population of Pakistan was 231.4 million (m) in 2021 of which almost 37.4 m population is urban. There is a huge rise of 1.8% in population by every year. Pakistan is 5th largest populated country of the world (World Bank, 2021). In order to meet the need of quality education of rapidly growing population, the traditional way of teaching does not suffice to meet the new challenges of the world. The ICT integration into the teaching learning is the ray of hope for developing the overall academic performance and to cope with the new social and technological development.

Over the past decade, Pakistan has witnessed a swift increase in the use of ICT (Chandio 2021). Since inception, the government has been putting efforts to revolutionize and bring reforms in educational sector. It helps Pakistani citizens in building up the IT competency to cope with challenges of the contemporary world. Additionally, IT Ministry has also established IT departments at provincial level to promote IT infrastructure and its education across the county. Government of Pakistan is focusing on IT infrastructure development, human resource development and provision of improved service to the citizen. However, institutions have adopted diverse levels where some have more IT based infrastructure than others (Ali et al. 2018).

The National Education Policy of Pakistan 1998-2008, shows an organized effort to integrate ICT for teaching-learning process but sadly it could not materialized due to lack of commitment to the cause and funds (MOFEPT 1998). Similarly, focus on ICT integration is also reflected in National Education Policy of Pakistan 2017-2025. This policy emphasizes to reshape teaching- learning and education management services while integrating ICT towards the needs of individual fulfilment and sustainable development of knowledge economy (MOFEPT 2017).

Higher Education Commission (HEC) of Pakistan also facilitates the development of higher education system in the country to be the focal point of research, development and high learning through ICT. HEC advises the use of ICT based applications for teaching and learning process and the same were encouraged during Covid-19 in Pakistan (Chandio 2021). The open and distance learning (ODL) policy of HEC 2023, shows an organize efforts to run ODL degree programs at par of the other regular degree programs by the universities. Higher education plays a significant role in socio-economic development of the society. However, current society demands for accepting new challenges and opportunities that is brought about by the revolution of ICT (Tilak 2015). Pakistan, to be successful in the 21st century, needs to design & implement an effective and robust ICT policy for higher education. The adaptation of ICT for higher education is crucial at present day order to meet the requirements of digital transformation and sustainable development goals.

2. Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The existing body of literature offers various theories, frameworks, and models pertinent to this investigation. However, this study follows the "Technological Pedagogical and Content Knowledge" (TPACK) framework introduced by Mishra and Koehler in 2006. This framework underscores the significance of integrating technological knowledge (TK) with content and pedagogical knowledge to enhance the effectiveness of teaching and learning practices (Bariu and Chun 2022). The adoption of the TPACK framework addresses challenges related to comprehending subject matter contributes to the transformation of traditional teaching approaches into contemporary methodologies (Luhanya et al. 2017). Thus, the TPACK framework was deemed the most suitable for this study. Figure 1 provides a visualization of the following three domains of knowledge essential for integrating ICT into teaching and learning effectively:

- Content Knowledge (CK)
- Pedagogical Knowledge (PK)
- Technological Knowledge (TK)

Figure 1: TPACK framework presented by Mishra and Koehler (2006).

CK pertains to a deep understanding of the subject matter being taught or learned, encompassing expertise in the specific field. PK involves knowledge about instructional methods and learning strategies, encompassing skills like lesson planning, classroom management and assessment techniques that facilitate effective educational practices (Bariu & Chun 2022). Whereas, TK emphasizes on understanding and utilizing different technologies within an educational setting. This covers familiarity with tools such as the internet, smart boards, multimedia resources, and digital libraries, as well as the ability to leverage these tools to enhance teaching and learning, particularly in higher education (Ratheeswari 2018).

Koehler and Mishra (2006), emphasized the essential nature of constructing the "TPACK" framework to facilitate teaching, learning and assessment within educational institutions. As per this framework, educators who hold a solid foundation in subject knowledge (CK) and effective instructional methods (PK) are better equipped to successfully integrate technology into their teaching practices, resulting in improved outcomes (Afzal and Claude 2016). By merging technological knowledge (TK) with CK and PK, faculty can harness the potential of ICT tools to achieve optimal results across various learning environments.

In the contemporary world, conventional teaching methodologies must grow into contemporary approaches as seen in developed countries, in order to keep pace with the rapid evolution of education (Richard 2015). The traditional pedagogical approach that emphasis solely on content has now shifted, with digital tools being used to deliver lectures and engage students. Today, technology has become an integral part of the learning experience, benefiting both educators and students by providing access to the latest subject knowledge (Tsegay et al. 2022). Figure 1 highlights the importance of TPACK, which represents the cultivation of technological knowledge among faculty members, enabling them to create dynamic, attractive, and informative content. This framework stresses the integration of subject-specific content and activities using emerging ICT tools to facilitate effective learning.

Material and Methods

Mixed method was used in this empirical study to get answer to the research questions. Mix method is most popular and significant in social science research (Morgan 2007). The quantitative and qualitative aspects of a study can be best explain using mix method. It provides a platform to use both quantitative and qualitative method of data collection in one or a set of related studies (Antwi 2015). Moreover, mix method provides a complete understanding of the research problem than using a single type of method (Creswell 2014). Employing both qualitative and quantitative methodologies holds importance as they offer complementary strengths and facilitate triangulation, ensuring a comprehensive grasp of the ICT integration impact on teaching and learning.

In this study, qualitative approach was employed to collect data on the perceptions of both students and teachers regarding implementation of ICT for teaching and learning activities. The inclusion of qualitative approach alongside a quantitative one is driven by the recognition that students and teachers derive varied benefits from the integration of ICT in their academic pursuits (Creswell 2014). The result of the study of Oye et al. (2012), shows the true picture of acceptance and use of ICT in Nigeria public universities through the help of mix method research. The pragmatic nature of the study, ICT integration for teaching and learning in HEIs can be best explain with mix method. Keeping in view the epistemology and ontology of the research matter, mix method was adopted for better understanding of the research problem and its objectives.

The study scope has been restricted to Hazara region, as it is lacking basic ICT infrastructure, low internet speed and electricity problems. The region is located in North-East of Khyber Pakhunkhwa (KP) province, Pakistan. This region is characterized as mountainous region, having rough terrain are some grave reasons for poor internet connection and making it difficult to install and maintain infrastructure, such as cellular towers and fiber-optic cables etc (Shafique et al. 2015). Additionally, the distance between the user and the nearest cell tower or internet service provider is another factor for the quality of the connection. This study specifically focuses on the Universities of Hazara region that offer diverse disciplines and a wide range of programs. These Universities include Abbottabad University of Science & Technology (AUST), COMSATS University Islamabad (CUI), Abbottabad Campus, Hazara University Mansehra (HU) and University of Haripur (UoH). This diverse selection provides comprehensive understanding of ICT influence on teaching and learning and valuable insight into the best practices related to ICT integration.

Data Collection and Analysis

The participants were chosen using purposive sampling to ensure easy access to the selected universities and to facilitate data collection for the study. For this study the targeted population was permanent faculty such as Lecturers, Assistant professors, Associate professor and Professors employed in the selected HEIs of Hazara region and students enrolled in different study programs such as Ph.D, MS/Mphil, Master and BS.

Teachers serves as real implementers of the university policies and the design curriculum. Therefore, they hold a significant role in teaching & learning process.

Likewise, students engaged in the learning environment provide feedback on their experiences with the teaching and learning process. By including both faculty and students, provide comprehensive insights and perspective on ICT integration its impact on teaching and learning. This approach allowed holistic understanding of the perceptions, experiences and challenges related to ICT implementation across different levels of higher education within the target population. Total participants of this study were 120 teachers and 240 students from the selected universities. The questionnaires were randomly given to all participants. In total, 360 respondents were contacted and 323 out of 360 responded to the questionnaires, including 85 faculty and 238 students. Participants who possessed familiarity with any of the 21st century educational technologies outlined in Table 1 were eligible to take part in the study, while those lacking the requisite experience were excluded.

Table 1: Examples of information communication technologies for the 21st century classroom (suggested by Watty, 2016 and Rachael,2018)

No	Category of ICTs	Examples (Sources)
1	Learning Management System (LMS)	Moodle, Desire 2learn, Blackboard, iLearn System, MOOCs, Learning Care, MyLMS etc
2	Social Media	Blog, Twitter, Wikis, Facebook, Whatsapp, Youtube, Google Drive etc
3	Communication	Synchronous (Skype, Zoom, Google Chat, Adobe Connect, Blooms, Reminds etc) Asynchronous (Online Discussion borad, email, whatsapp, Telegram, We Chat etc)
4	Simulated Learning	Normalized Games, Legends of Learning, Classcraft, Animot etc
5	Mobile Technologies	Tablet, computer, Laptop, Smartphone (e.g iOS, Andriod)
6	Learning Styles	E-learning, Distance learning, Blended learning, mobile learning etc
7	Assessment Technologies	Quizlet, Quizlet Live, MOOCs, Google Forms, ZipGrade, Attendance Manager etc
8	Presentation and learning creation tools	Software (Microsoft Power point, Adobe Presenter, Google Slide, Adobe Acrobat Reader, Screen Capture etc
9	Learning Objects	e-books, Podcast, audio, video lectures, Flickr, Google Photos, QR Code scanner etc

Note: Participants were asked to denote "others" for ICT tools other than mentioned in table 1

The required primary data was collected through a well-structured questionnaire covering all the selected variables (availability of ICT, accessibility, usability, usefulness and teaching & learning) from both faculty and students. Participants were allowed to tick more than one option in ICT tools and platforms they use in teaching and learning. Primary data collection has been done during the study period from August 2022-November 2022. In alignment with ethical principles, the participants were duly informed about the study's objectives and the intended usage of the data. Adherence to university ethics and governance guidelines ensured the strict conservation of anonymity and confidentiality. It is important to note that the collected data's purpose was solely for academic pursuits.

Secondary data such as policies regarding ICT usage by the HEC Pakistan, IT related information, types of learning, region information and other studies results etc. has been collected from relevant government and institution's reports, publications, departments, websites, articles, books and available literatures etc. Secondary data has brought depth and strength to the analysis and made the process of analysis and result discussion more impactful.

Furthermore, the data was analyzed through descriptive statistics, thematic analysis, chi square test and logistic regression using SPSS version 27. At the first point the use of ICT in perceived areas of importance effecting teaching and learning were ranked. The ranking of the diverse area was computed with the principle of weighted average using the "Relative Importance Index" (RII) method. This method is helpful in computing the Likert scale data (Aibinu and Jagboro 2002). RII was calculated using following formula.

$$RII = \frac{\sum W}{(A * N)} \quad (1)$$

Where, RII represents the Relative Importance Index, W represents the assigned weight for each factor on a scale of 1 to 5 by the participants. A corresponds to the maximum weight, which is 5 in this scenario, and N denotes the overall count of participants. The weighted average for the two group respondents will be calculated based on the ranking (R) of relative indices (RI). These ranking can be further categorize into significant level. According to Akadiri (2011), RI values can be categorize into five levels; high (H) ($0.8 \leq RI \leq 1$), high-medium (H-M) ($0.6 \leq RI \leq 0.8$), medium (M) ($0.4 \leq RI \leq 0.6$), medium-low (M-L) ($0.2 \leq RI \leq 0.4$), and low (L) ($0 \leq RI \leq 0.2$).

Moreover, in the diverse regression forms, logistic regression is considered appropriate to carried out particularly, when the dependent variable is deemed binary(Yes/No) (Connelly 2020). This technique is helpful in identifying important factors impacting the target variable and the nature of relationship between these factors and dependent variable. Thus, logistic regression was employed to predict the probability effects of the independent variables' impacting the dependent variable:

$$\text{Logit}(Y) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 \dots \dots \dots + \beta_n X_n \quad (2)$$

Where Y is the dependent variable (impact on teaching and learning), indicating the likelihood that Y=1 otherwise 0, α = the intercept, $\beta_1 \dots \dots \beta_n$ = coefficients of the associated independent variables, $X_1 \dots \dots X_n$ = independent variables; X1= availability of ICT, X2= accessibility, X3= usability, X4= usefulness. Logistic regression was conducted to ascertain the relationship between ICT integration determinants and teaching and learning in HEIs. The threshold for significant value was 0.05. Any value higher than 0.05 was considered not applicable, while any value below 0.05 was seen to have considerable impact.

3. Results

Table 2: Demographic information of the respondents

	Demographic	Frequency	%age
Respondents	Faculty	85	26
	Students	238	74
Gender	Male	232	72
	Female	91	28
Age	Less than 20 years	37	11
	21-25 years	127	40
	26-30 years	27	8
	More than 30 years	132	41
Education	B.S	155	48
	Master	7	2
	MS/MPhil	61	19
	PhD	100	31
University	AUST	74	23
	COMSATS	105	32
	HAZARA	77	24
	HARIPUR	67	21
Digital gadgets	Laptop	100	31

	Computer	46	14
	Smart phone	173	54
	Digital pen	4	1
ICT in Daily Life	Educational Information	125	42
	Messaging & Chatting	47	13
	Social Media	105	31
	Movies	33	10
	Music	13	4

The total respondents in this study are 323 out of these 26% are faculty and 74% of them are students. Result in table 2 shows that 232 (72%) participants were male while 91(28%) were female. The higher percentage of male students indicate the higher enrolment rate of male students in the region as compared to the female students. Moreover, majority 132 (41%) of the total respondents are more than 30 years of age. The higher age of a respondent can significantly impact in research and can influence various aspects of the study such as; perspective and experience, cognitive abilities and life stage consideration. However, 127 (40%) respondents were from 21 to 25 years of age. Furthermore, maximum responses 151(48%) were received from B.S students followed by PhD 100 (31%) and minimum responses received from Master 7(2%). The maximum response rate is observed from COMSATS university Abbottabad campus 105(32%) followed by Hazara university 77(24%) and low response rate 74 (23%) received from AUST and 67 (21%) from university of Haripur respectively.

Likewise, table 2 provides insights into the digital devices owned by the participants. According to the data, a significant proportion of respondents, up to 54%, possess smartphones. This device plays a pivotal role in respondents' engagement with educational content, social media interaction, messaging, and communication. The widespread utilization of smartphones facilitates continuous access to information and various data sources. The dataset also highlights that laptops are personally owned by 31% of the respondents, and recognized as essential tools for purposes like teaching, learning, and research. Maximum response for smartphones and laptops displayed the importance and maximum utilization of these digital gadgets for both teaching and learning in HEIs in the Hazara region. In contrast, the utilization of traditional computers is indicated by a response rate of only 14%. This low figure reflects the growing trend of smartphones and laptops, which offer enhanced portability, compact size, and versatile functionalities, ultimately diminishing the prominence of desktop computers. Interestingly, a mere only 1% of respondents report ownership of digital pens. Besides, the application of ICT tools extends beyond the classroom environment and were examined in relation to daily life. Table 2 shows that, 42% of the respondents employ ICT for obtaining educational information, while 31% utilize digital devices for engaging in social media activities. Notably, 13% of respondents use ICT for messaging and chatting, while 10% resort to it for watching movies, and 4% for listening the music.

Table 3: Respondents ICT usage for teaching & learning (n=323)

ICT Profile		Frequency	%age	Chi-Square Value	P-Value
ICTs usage for teaching and learning	Rarely used	6	1.9	17.11	0.00***
	Occasionally used	15	4.6	44.04	0.00***
	Frequently used	135	41.8	7.27	0.00***
	use all the time	167	51.7	0.99	0.31
Type of ICT tools	Smart board	34	10.5	0.71	0.39
	Multimedia Projector	256	79.3	22.93	0.00***

	Smart phone	198	61.3	9.86	0.00***
	Laptop	152	47.1	23.13	0.00***
	Digital pen	9	2.8	0.08	0.77
	Note pad or Tablet	30	9.3	6.58	0.01**
	Desktop Computer	112	34.7	19.12	0.00***
	Smart Television	12	3.7	0.59	0.43
	Video device Camera	3	0.9	2.54	0.11
	Sound device	7	2.2	3.50	0.06*
	Software and applications	84	26.0	6.87	0.00***
	Others	2	0.6	0.51	0.47
Educational Technology Platforms	Learning Management System (LMS)	158	48.9	17.22	0.00***
	Collaborative Technologies or Social Media	130	40.2	03.06	0.08*
	Simulated Learning	19	5.9	0.28	0.59
	Mobile Technologies	174	53.9	4.33	0.03**
	E-learning or Distance Learning	131	40.6	2.82	0.09
	Assessment Technologies	90	27.9	0.22	0.63
	Presentation and learning creation tools	155	48.0	18.94	0.00***

Note: *** signifies 1%, ** 5% and * 10% level of significance (** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$)

Table 3 summarize the respondents' ICTs usage of the 21st century technologies. A significant number of participants 51.7% acknowledged utilizing ICTs consistently in their teaching endeavors, while 41.8% respondents use it frequently and 4.6% use it occasionally. Almost half of the respondents use ICTs on regular basis that indicates the importance of the digital gadgets for teaching and learning. Among the technological tools employed, Laptops, Smartphones and Multimedia projectors stood out as the most frequently used devices. In contrast, desktop computers, software and applications saw infrequent use. Smart televisions, interactive whiteboards, tablets, video cameras and audio devices ranked lowest in terms of usage frequency. The low percentage of these gadgets shows the inadequate availability and use for teaching and learning purposes. In relation to technological platforms, the majority of respondents (53.9%) made use of mobile technologies, followed by Learning Management Systems (LMSs) (48.9%) and presentation and learning creation tools (48.0%).

Other technology platforms such as learning styles or approaches, assessment or evaluation tools and collaborative technologies exhibited moderate levels of utilization. Research findings are further explained with the help of chi-square test to get more clarity on the result analysis. Result presented in table 3 highlights that, the item ICT usage for teaching and learning has a significant p-value (0.00) at 1% for almost all the points, which displays a significant association between ICT usage and respondents. Further, the chi-square test affirms the significant p-value (0.00) for ICT tools such as; multimedia projector, smartphones, laptops, computers, and software & applications. The compelling values of these tools highlight the extensive adoption of these items for teaching and learning by the respondents in higher education setups. Moreover, the results also validate the significant p-value (0.00) for educational technology platforms such as; LMS, Mobile technologies and presentation learning creation tools. These significant values emphasize that respondents are not only incline towards but also extensively utilize these technological platforms to harness the potential of ICT tools within the learning environment. Similarly, a p-value $> (0.00)$ was also observed across all the items in various categories indicates an absence of statistical significance, suggesting a moderate to low level of utilization of ICT tools and technological platforms by the educators and learners.

Faculty and students in HEIs are to be encouraged to adopt educational technology, as it play important and significant role in influencing people's lives and activities(Bariu and Chun 2022). The increased availability of advance technology advocates its more frequent utilization (Allison2022). The qualitative findings on respondents' perspectives regarding application of 21st century educational technology indicate a general agreement on its positive implication when optimally utilized and integrated into the curriculum:

A common response was observed from the respondent's data that "the use of ICT tools is a good practice as it reduces paper usage, accommodate student's need, improve knowledge and prepare them for industry revolution (IR 4.0) if it becomes mutual practice in the classroom". The importance of ICT cannot be ignored particularly, in the field of education. It provides various benefits not only to the students and faculty but also the administration such as it save time, reduce paper wastage, easy communication, use for getting feedback and timely information. Similarly, it also provides an environment for the students and faculty to prepare themselves for industry revolution and to compete in the market. Similarly, when students were asked about ICT tools and its usage a common opinion were observed as "multimedia projector, smartphones, laptops, computers, and LMS are frequently used in the learning environment". The fascinating values of these tools highlight the extensive adoption of these items for teaching and learning by the respondents in higher education setups.

A common response were observed from Professors that "teaching with educational technology has been a positive experience, contributing to the improvement of the education system. However, I recognize the need to acquire additional skills in this domain. The utilization of technology among young lecturers and junior staff in the teaching process shows great promise". This highlights the importance and lack of adequate training at institutional level for the faculty to involve them in the efficient use of these tools. Provision of regular training of the faculty will help and motivate them to efficiently use ICTs for teaching and learning.

Ranking of the Perceived Learning and Teaching Factors

Both the group of respondents highlights 25 areas (11 out of 25 for teaching and 14 out of 25 learning) of importance where the use of ICT brings improvement and impacts their teaching and learning. When students were asked about their perception of ICT use for learning, they highlight their perceived areas of importance such as "learning and academic performance, communicate with teachers, development of skills and vocabulary, and distance learning etc"(see table 4). Students ranked the statement "Internet and computer improve learning and academic performance" number one. This displays that the presence and use of internet and computer play very important role in students' academic performance and overall learning. Furthermore, the requirements of the graduate students particularly, at the university level make the use of internet and computer more important for their projects and research etc. The studies of Raman (2018), Erdogdu (2015) and Akele (2014), also proved that use of internet and computer has positive and strong effect on students learning and performance. Moreover, students also perceived that ICT can bring improvement and positive impact on communication with the teachers, vocabulary building and distance learning. Students also low ranked some statements such as "I learn computer skills more inside the institution than outside" which indicates that learning takes place irrespective of the location if they are provided with the ICT tools. The rank wise response of the students for each area and its importance is given in table 4.

Table 4: Students perceived factors of ICT use for learning

Students perception on ICT use for learning	Score	RII	Ranks (R)
I learn computer skills more inside the institution than outside	885	0.7436	13
ICT help to understand lectures through pictorial and graphical presentation	962	0.8084	3
ICT Tools provides new ways of learning	874	0.7344	14
Internet and computer improve learning and academic performance	972	0.8168	1
ICT help in academic research, online searches and downloading articles etc	946	0.7949	8
Digital library and computer labs are helping sources of learning	951	0.7991	6
Institution portal helps in online discussion	902	0.7579	11
Online learning resources made me neglect from traditional learning sources	921	0.7739	10
I learn difficult vocabulary and concepts using ICT	958	0.8050	4
Use of ICT hinders my interpersonal skills in classroom	896	0.7529	12
Smart board increases learning	949	0.7974	7
technology provides opportunities to effectively communicate with the teachers	965	0.8109	2
ICT helps in distance learning	953	0.8008	5
ICT use has declined my writing skills	926	0.7781	9

The above table 4 findings are corroborated by the qualitative analysis's findings. Integration of ICT in education provides students with a more interactive and engaged learning environment and opportunities to develop digital literacy and other 21st century skills (Irfan Naufal, 2015). The availability of modern ICT infrastructure is a crucial factor in enhancing the quality of education and facilitating student learning in the 21st century. During the survey students of different programs particularly, BS programs took keen interest in the study. Both male and female students were of the opinion that ICTs bring improvement in their learning and in academic performance. A common opinion observed among the students that "ICT tools are important sources to improve leaning and academic performance. It is also used for obtaining latest information, distance learning, graphical representation, vocabulary building and for communication and social engagement etc". ICT in the field of education has eased students in accessing the learning materials such as access to e-books, past papers, research information, content related materials to improve their learning and academic performance etc (Sharma 2011). Similarly, ICT provides a great flexibility in education to ensure that learners are able to access knowledge regardless of space and time (Akele 2014).

Table 5: Teachers perceived factors of ICT use for teaching (n=85)

Teachers perception on ICT use for teaching	Total	RII	Ranks
Enhance computer and teaching skills	360	0.8470	3
Team work collaboration and communication with people	366	0.8611	2
ICT help me in achieving curriculum objectives	245	0.5764	10
Getting new and supporting information on the subject	381	0.8964	1
I feel confident and comfortable while using ICT	274	0.6447	8
I feel comfortable with pedagogical aspects of ICT	253	0.5952	9
Students with learning disabilities were involve when ICT was used	299	0.7035	7
Students were motivated when I used ICT	309	0.7270	6
Technical issues were resolved quickly when I needed help	203	0.4776	11
Delivering lectures to students	349	0.8211	4
Getting feedback from the students	340	0.8000	5

Furthermore, when teachers were asked about their perception of ICT use for teaching, they highlight their perceived areas of importance such as “development of skills and communication, presentations, getting information and delivering lectures, and getting feedback from the students etc” (see table 5). Teachers top-ranked the statement “Getting new information on the subject”. It highlights that teachers are more concern for their lecture delivery, making the best use of gadgets for obtaining relevant material and new information to make the lecture more presentable, informative and easy understandable for the students. The studies of Kunwar et al. (2022), Erjabo et al. (2021) and Plomp et al. (2007), also proved that use of ICTs are important contemporary sources of getting new information and help teachers and students to get supporting material particularly on the subject matter. Moreover, teachers also perceived other areas important like; collaboration and communication with people, enhance teaching and computer skills and help in delivering effective lecture, where the use of ICT has positive effect. Teachers also low ranked some statements such as “Technical issues were resolved quickly when I needed help” which indicates that faculty face problems in resolving the technical issues when it arises in the classroom. The inadequate technical assistance and quick availability of technical staff were observed an important challenge and barrier in the efficient use of ICT for teaching. The rank wise response of the teachers for each area and its importance is given in table 5.

The above quantitative findings in table 5 is supported by the qualitative findings. During the survey a common perception among the faculty that “ICT is useful for effective lecture delivery, getting new and supporting information on the subject, enhance skills and team work collaboration, if universities authorities ensure adequate availability, provision of uninterrupted internet connectivity and strict compliance on implementation policy”. A similar result of the perception was found in the study of Khan et al., (2019), state that the availability of ICT resources such as computers, internet access, and software applications significantly impact the quality of teaching and learning in HEIs. Teachers’ perceived usefulness of technology seems to have a direct significant effect on their intention to use it (Oye et al. 2014).

Similarly, another common perception received on usability of ICT from faculty that “ICT tools are important sources in delivering lectures but lack of proper training to the faculty on use of ICTs is the major concern that has negatively affected the ICTs implementations in the classroom environment at one hand and demotivation of the faculty on the other hand”. This highlights the importance and lack of adequate training at institutional level for the faculty to involve them in the efficient use of these tools. Such training will enable both faculty and students to make effective use of these tools, which will ultimately enhance teaching and learning process”. According to the study of Alghizzawi et al. (2019), the utilization of diverse digital devices like smartphones, laptops, personal computers, and tablets has led to heightened interaction between teachers and students through online content sharing, lecture notes, assignments, and feedback. This increased connectivity has effectively enhanced the learning experiences of both students and teachers.

Regression Analysis

Table 6: ICT determinants influencing teaching and learning

Perceived effect on Teaching & Learning	ICT Determinants	Coefficient	Standard Error	Wald	P-Value	Exp (β)
Teaching	Availability of ICTs	1.85	.917	4.09	0.04	6.40
	Access to ICTs	-33.25	213.27	0.00	0.99	0.00
	Usability of ICTs	22.07	73.70	0.00	0.01	1.44
	Usefulness of ICTs	1.25	0.87	2.05	0.15	3.50
Learning	Availability of ICTs	0.02	0.26	0.00	0.93	1.02
	Access to ICTs	0.44	0.24	3.31	0.04	1.56
	Usability of ICTs	2.04	0.32	38.60	0.00	7.73
	Usefulness of ICTs	0.71	0.24	8.64	0.00	2.04

The impact of individual element of ICT integration on teaching and learning was investigated through using logistic regression analysis. The result of regression model highlight the coefficients and significant effect of each variable. The availability of ICT have positive and significant effect on teaching ($X^2=1.85$, $p=0.04$). It exhibits that availability of ICT tools in the classroom make the teaching process more effective. The availability of modern ICT infrastructure is a crucial factor in enhancing the quality of education and facilitating student and teachers in their learning. Different studies found that the availability of ICT infrastructure and its usefulness in educational institutions is a key factor in determining the effectiveness of ICT in teaching and learning (Khan et al., 2019; Kumar 2020 and Hossain et al. 2021). A similar result was also found in the analysis for ICT usability, the positive and significant effect of ICT usability on teaching was examined ($X^2=22.07$, $p=0.00$) in the classroom. It highlights that the usability of the ICT tools make the teaching process more effective and significant.

Similarly, a positive and significant impact of ICT elements were also found on students learning, where the coefficient and p-values of ICT elements such as; accessibility, usability and usefulness were ($X^2=0.44$, $p=0.04$), ($X^2=2.04$, $p=0.00$) and ($X^2= 0.71$, $p=0.00$) respectively. These result exhibits that the use of ICT is important for students learning and their academic performance. The easy accessibility of ICT tools in classrooms, computer labs and in central library provide them an opportunity to enhance their technical and knowledge skills. The significant values of the variables slike usability and usefulness highlights that student's ability to use more the ICT tools the more learning will take place, which will ultimately enhances their academic performance. Research also shows that the availability of ICT infrastructure, its easy access and usefulness in educational institutions enhances students learning and academic performance (Conole et al. 2008; Jaiswal 2020 and Hossain et al. 2021).

4. Discussion

Result shows that a significant number of faculty and students 51.7% uses all the time the ICT tools for educational purposes like Computers, Laptops, Smartphones, Multimedia projectors, Smart boards, Cameras and Audio devices etc. This trend indicates a transformation shift in the process of teaching and learning, making them more engaging and interactive. This finding of the analysis support the study conducted by Alghizzawi et al. (2019) and Perienen (2020), stated that the use of various digital gadgets has led to an increased interaction between faculty and students. This interaction is facilitated through activities like sharing online content, distributing lecture notes, assigning tasks and providing feedback. This enhanced connectivity has had a positive impact on the learning experiences of both students and teachers.

This research work has also discovered that 79.3% of the faculty uses ICT tools particularly multimedia projectors and power points for delivering lectures to attract students' attention for improved learning. These findings align with the conclusion drawn from the studies of Geraldin (2022) and Isman (2010). Furthermore, results indicate that the use of internet contributes significantly to enhancing both students' and teachers' level of motivation, as well as overall learning and access to information. This finding strengthens the study of Alkhawaldeh et al. (2023), states that ICT for e-learning increases the learners' critical thinking ability and empowers them to engage in independent learning. Similarly, it also validates the study of Chang (2016) that students' effective learning occurs with the use of internet as an ICT tool. Further, this demonstrates the multifaceted advantages of incorporating ICT tools and resources, such as multimedia projectors, the internet, and other various devices, to enhance engagement, interactivity, and overall educational experiences for both students and educators.

The study employed various methodologies such as RII, Chi-square tests, thematic analysis and logistic regression to explore the relationship between ICT integration and its impact on teaching and learning, where the result of the analysis demonstrated a positive and significant association between ICT determinants; availability of ICT, usability, accessibility & usefulness and teaching and learning. The study also identified several factors related to ICT integration that significantly influence teaching and learning in higher education. The findings of RII, ranked the importance of each factor and the binary logistic regression analysis further confirmed the importance of these ICT determinants in shaping the educational process within higher education. These findings are in line with the studies of Geraldin (2022) and Ayuso-Del (2022), states that integration of digital technologies has a positive and strong effect on teaching and learning and also develops an environment of digital literacy. This substantial role of ICT enables students and faculty to efficiently search, consult and retrieve different information.

Furthermore, results of the research support the TPACK framework presented by Kohler and Mishra. According to the framework, effective teaching and learning depends on the association of technology and faculty. For effective teaching, it depends on three domains of knowledge. TPACK is the connection of three types of knowledge such as Technological knowledge, Content knowledge and Pedagogical knowledge. The development of such TPACK by the faculty is essential for effective teaching and learning as shown in figure 1. The same has been proved in this research and results express that effective teaching and learning depends on ICT integration as mentioned in table 4 and 5. It was found that faculty uses technology to get new information and material on the subject matter that develops their technical and teaching skills. The use of technology by the faculty in teaching methodology makes their lecture and its delivery more interactive and engaged.

According to RII and regression analysis, also indicate a positive and significant association between ICT and teaching and learning in HEIs of the Hazara region as shown in table 4, 5 and 6. The top ranked statements in both table 4 and 5 highlight the importance of ICT usage for teaching and learning. Moreover, the positive and significant values in table 6 indicate the positive impact of ICT variables on teaching and learning. These findings get support from the study of Dexter et al. (2012). The alignment between the TPACK framework and the current study's findings highlights the importance of developing a comprehensive understanding of the interplay between technology, content, and pedagogy for successful educational outcomes. The synergy of these domains, as represented by TPACK, is integral to fostering enhanced teaching methods and enriched learning experiences within the context of HEIs in the Hazara region.

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6. Conclusion

The ICT revolution has brought a massive impact particularly, on education sector throughout the world. The introduction of ICT tools have attracted a lot of interest in higher education as they offer promising avenues to enhance teaching, learning, research, information access and academic performance. The same was also proved in this study, where RII top ranked result in both table 4 and 5 highlights the importance and use of ICT tools for teaching and learning. Today, ICT offers solution to address issues related to collaboration, information access, communication and diverse teaching & learning methods.

Besides, this research verifies the transformative potential of ICT tools and resources, such as multimedia projectors, power point presentations, smart boards, laptops and internet access, in revolutionizing teaching methodologies. These tools not only empower faculty members to deliver engaging and interactive lectures but also captivate students' attention, thereby enhancing overall learning outcomes. Moreover, the study highlights the integral role of the internet in elevating motivation levels, fostering independent learning, and facilitating improved access to information for both students and educators.

The result demonstrates the positive and significant relationship between the integration of ICT and teaching and learning experiences. The results of the regression model underscore the significance of ICT determinants, specifically the availability and usability of ICTs, in influencing teaching. The findings reveal that the presence of ICT tools in the classroom has a positive impact on the teaching process, enhancing its effectiveness. Additionally, the positive and significant value associated with ICT usability indicates a promising influence on teaching. Similarly, a positive and significant impact of ICT elements were also found on students learning.

The study findings are also important as they align closely with the TPACK framework, highlighting the crucial interconnection of technology, content, and pedagogy in facilitating impactful education. The findings emphasize that it is imperative for faculty to cultivate a robust TPACK framework that seamlessly integrates technological expertise with content ability and pedagogical skill. By aligning with this framework, educators can harness the full potential of ICT integration to create dynamic and impactful learning experiences.

ICT and its knowledge is indispensable for individuals to actively participate in society and to excel in their fields. It is believed that ICT forms the foundation for lifelong learning as an outcome to the introduction to digital information. In this process educators can play a crucial role in promoting ICT based learning. Findings of the study indicate lack of training in the institutions. Therefore, HEIs must reevaluate the value of ICT as a tool and provision of ICT based training to enhance the process of teaching and learning. The research not only contributes to the academic discourse on effective teaching and learning but also provides valuable insights for educational policymakers and institutions aiming to harness the benefits of ICT integration to elevate the standards of higher education in the Hazara region and beyond.

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